

Scientific Interpretation of the Issues of Treatment And Communication In The Research of Uzbek Psychologists

Raximova E`tibor Rustamovna,
Urgench state university
E mail: Etibor-r@mail.ru

Abstract

This article includes the opinions of Uzbek psychologists about communication in their research. It was studied by them that priority is given to the issues of dialogue and communication in the development of a person, and a lot of information about the issues of dialogue and communication was presented.

Key words: dialogue, treatment, communication, personality development, friendly attitude, rules of conduct, education, friendship.

Introduction

It emphasizes that the exchange of information and the establishment of relationships are significantly influenced by the manners and methods of communication. The text also highlights the need to understand the factors shaping interpersonal communication and the mechanisms that influence them, underlining the urgency of this issue. Furthermore, it mentions that in the scientific heritage of Eastern thinkers, the formation and development of an individual's personality, and their education and upbringing hold a crucial position.

Communication and interpersonal interaction issues are significant in all eras. about, information sharing, management, and communication all play significant roles while starting a relationship. We can draw the conclusion that communication is a process that is produced between people, and that the way a problem functions is determined by studying the factors that affect it. Numerous studies carried out by the scientists in our country have helped to control this aspect of behavior and human connections.

ANALYZING LITERATURE

In her social psychology research, V. Karimova [7] focuses on behavior and communication problems. He claims that it is clear that he founded his author's perspective on an examination of the ideas of dialogue, communication, and therapy. Furthermore, the characteristics of communication and their particular manifestations in human action are demonstrated, as well as the socio-psychological factors that influence the development of communication in the human personality. E. G. Goziyev [6] made an effort to address communication-related concerns in his "Transactional Psychology" handbook. The author of the handbook emphasizes conduct as the cornerstone of human activity and concentrates on elucidating the psychological processes that underlie both the development of personality and behavior. More broadly, extensive scientific research in this area has been made possible by the development of scientific research methodologies for assessing an individual's communication skill development.

One of our experts, P.S. Ergashev [4], proposed a novel method for his communication research. In his methodical handbook "Communication psychology," he elucidated the meaning of the notions of communication and communication and attempted to support the distinctions between them. The handbook specifically presents theoretical and empirical perspectives on the notion of communication's content, as well as its features, roles, and tasks, as well as age-related development characteristics. In addition, a person receives rigorous recommendations for improving their communicative talents as well as psychodiagnostic techniques.

DISCUSSION

F.A. Akramova [1] presented her author's approach in this area and concentrated on the topics of behavior, attitude, interaction, and communication in her studies on social psychology. It should be highlighted at this point that rational concepts are used to describe how a person is introduced to social processes, how important communication is to his embodiment as an engaged member of society, and how his development is determined by his age and activity. It should be highlighted that when communication is focused on the individual and relates to meeting their intense informational demands, it is relevant and successful.

Research on the topic "Formation of individual behavior style in adolescents during the educational process" was conducted by E.I. Ganeyeva [12], with the goal of examining the psychological mechanisms behind the development of unique behavior style and how it contributes to the development of adolescents' individuality. Additionally, within the parameters of the study, the role of individual style in the development of teens' integral individuality is examined, with consideration given to the ethno-cultural component, and the individual treatment style within the framework of teens' integral uniqueness. Additionally, the unique characteristics of how pupils' particular behaviors are formed during the educational process are explained. Specifically, research has demonstrated that group work arrangements made during the schooling process can be one of the strategies for raising the teen's individual behavior development level. Simultaneously, it was demonstrated that educators and psychologists may employ the created program for the development of individual behavior when assisting secondary school teachers.

In the study "Psychoprophylaxis and psychocorrection of the formation of the feeling of loneliness in adolescents" by N.Sh. Mullaboyeva [8], the development of the feeling of loneliness in adolescence is typified by poor communication skills, low self-esteem, and an incapacity to fit in with a group. examined for a relationship with Teenage loneliness can also be caused by a variety of

sociopsychological factors, such as social adaptability, the development of a positive self-image in relation to communication problems, self-awareness, increased communicative competence, and close relationships with peers. It is demonstrated to be connected to individual traits.

The scientific research work on "The influence of interpersonal relations in the family on the child's social perception" by G.A. Kurbanova [11] revealed, based on empirical research, that the nature of a child's communication process is influenced by interpersonal relations in the family and is dependent on feelings of sympathy or antipathy. Specifically, research has focused on how early adolescence and adolescence's distinct interpersonal interaction traits present themselves, as well as the psychological aspects of adolescent social perception.

The influence of the adolescent sibling status in the group effects has been studied. The sociopsychological characteristics of the relationships of adolescents with different sibling status with their peers were investigated in N.A. Gayibova's scientific research work [5] on the topic "Social-psychological characteristics of the relationships of adolescents with different sibling status with their peers" using scientific research methods.

RESULT.

It should be highlighted that teenagers' relationships with their peers have unique sociopsychological traits. Examples of situations that illustrate the sociopsychological, sexual, and gender characteristics of how an adolescent's position in the family affects the group's influence include first-born. Compared to their siblings, children are more responsible for handling dispute resolution; also, older children tend to have more controlling relationships with peers, while younger children are more talkative and highly influential within the group. was discovered to be. It is also well known that teenage relationships with their peers are directly impacted by sibling relationships, which are highly valued in the home. Additionally, studies show that children who are raised alone and do not have siblings struggle to adjust to changing social circumstances. It is also well known that teenage relationships with their peers are directly impacted by sibling relationships, which are highly valued in the home. Additionally, studies show that children who are raised alone and do not have siblings struggle to adjust to changing social circumstances.

By establishing the affiliation motive, N.T. Norkulova's [9] scientific research study on the subject "Affiliation motive - a social-psychological factor that forms the moral image of students" seeks to understand the socio-psychological elements that impact the development of the moral image of students. concentrated. Specifically, the elements of orientation to affiliation and fear of rejection, the relationship between the affiliation motive and knowledge, cognitive and integrative processes, and self-emphasis have been identified as factors in the creation of students' moral image. Additionally, the sociopsychological traits of conduct and communication in the context of forming connections and collaborating are demonstrated. Additionally, throughout the student time, diagnostic techniques for doing empirical research on how social behavior and spirituality are influenced by the affiliation motive were established. Because of this, corporate and sociopsychological trainings on how pupils establish their spiritual identities were created with affiliation as the driving force.

The objective of M.F. Dadakhodjayeva's scientific research work on the topic "Psychological characteristics of the formation of behavior in college students" is to examine the distinctiveness of the sociability of vocational college students as well as the characteristics of the formation of behavior in them. According to the study's framework, communication is regarded as one of the primary manifestations of the psyche, alongside behavior and activity. Communication's functional attributes show up as the communicator's communicative, systematic transfer of information, which is a part of the

educational process. It was also demonstrated that the development of dealing etiquette is a system with a hierarchical structure of complicated material that goes through specific phases, stages, levels, indicators, and criteria. Specifically, empirical research has shown that communicativeness is a characteristic that guarantees the stability of the communication process in the form of a person's skill or fluency (student).

Anvarova, D.M. [2] The scientific research work titled "Psychological characteristics of the formation and development of the spirituality of teenagers" reveals the measures taken to investigate the psychological mechanisms behind the formation and development of teenagers' spirituality and to ensure that this process is effective. given Additionally, a methodical approach to the formation and development of teens' spirituality, as well as the step-by-step objectives and techniques for its growth, were developed as part of the research project.

Determining the function of example, social-psychological traits, and forms in the socialization of teenagers is the main goal of N.D. Kasimova's scientific research work on the topic "Importance of socio-psychological characteristics of example in the socialization of adolescents" [10]. Based on empirical research, it has become clear how values, social norms, and traditions are socialized, especially throughout adolescence. These norms are formed by learning from specific people and creative symbols.

CONCLUSION.

The aforementioned points demonstrate the breadth of research that Uzbek psychologists have conducted on communication. Therefore, it provides the opportunity to draw the following conclusions:

- a person's communication formation is determined by their place in the social relations system;
- based on the studies of scientists who have conducted scientific research on adolescent problems, they have covered the following topics: etiquette, the motivation behind affiliation, socialization, communication formation, and peer relations.

List of literature:

1. Akramova F.A., Ijtimoiy psixologiya: o'quv qo'llanmasi. – T.:TDPU, 2007. – 166 b.
2. Anvarova D.M., O'smirlar ma'naviyati shakllanishi va rivojlanishining psixologik xususiyatlari – Psixol. f.n...dis. – T.: TDPU, 2011, – 136 b.
3. Dadaxodjayeva M.F., Kollej o'quvchilarida muomala maromi shakllanishining psixologik xususiyatlari Psixol. f. n...dis. Avtoref – T.: – 2012.-23 b.
4. Ergashev P., Muloqot psixologiyasi (ma'ruzalar matni). T.: Yozuvchi, 2003.-197 b.
5. G'ayibova N.A., Turli sibling maqomidagi o'smirlarning tengdoshlari bilan munosabatlarning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari. Psixol. f. n...dis. Avtoref – T.: TDPU – 2019. – 23 b.
6. G'oziyev E.G., Muomala psixologiyasi. T.:Sharq, 2001.-140 b.
7. Karimova V.M., Ijtimoiy psixologiya. –T.: «Fan va texnologiya», 2012, 172 b.
8. Mullaboyeva N.Sh., O'smirlarda yolg'izlik hissi shakllanishining psixoprofilaktikasi va psixokorreksiyasi Psixol. f. n.dis...avtoref – T.:TDPU – 2019. – 24 b.
9. Norkulova, N.T., Affiliatsiya motivi - talabalar ma'naviy qiyofasini shakllantiruvchi ijtimoiy - psixologik omili. Psixol. f. n...dis. Avtoref – T.: O'zMU – 2018. 22-b.
10. Qosimova N.D., O'smirlar ijtimoiylashuvida ibrat ijtimoiy psixologik xususiyatlarining ahamiyati Psixol. f. n...dis. Avtoref – T.: O'zMU – 2010. – 23 b.
11. Qurbonova G.A., Oiladagi shaxslararo munosabatlarning farzand ijtimoiy persepsiyasiga ta'siri" tasviriy san'at yo'nalishidagi tahsil olayotgan o'quvchilar misolida Psixol. f. n...dis. Avtoref – T.: TDPU – 2008. – 23 b.

12. Ганеева Э.И., Формирование индивидуального стиля общения у подростков в учебно – воспитательном процессе: Автореф. дис... канд. психол. наук. – Ташкент: НУУз, 2002, – 24 с.
13. Raximova E.R., O'smir muloqotidagi psixologik qiyinchiliklar diagnostikasi va korreksiyasi. – Psixol. f.b...PhD dis. Avtorefer – T.: TDPU, 2023, – 19 b. <http://library.ziyonet.uz/uz/book/127453>
14. Saidmuratova M.B. Bolalarda kitob o'qishga qiziqishni shakllantirishning psixologik xususiyatlari. – Psixol. f.b...PhD dis. Avtorefer – T.: TDPU, 2023, – 22 b. <http://library.ziyonet.uz/uz/book/127434>